

Effect of Structural Changes in the Chromophoric Chain in the Dyes derived from Benzimidazoles

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In the present investigation, several *p*-dialkylamino styryldyes and their corresponding diaza analogues have been prepared from substituted benzimidazoles to study the effect of replacement of $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$ by $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ in the chromophoric chain, on absorption of these dyes. The absorption data have been discussed in the light of Forster's rule. Besides a number of azo dyes, which may also be regarded as diaza analogues mentioned above, have been prepared for dyeing synthetic fibres.

In course of our investigation on the influence of structural changes on absorption, it was considered of interest to study the effect of replacement of $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$ by $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ in the chromophoric chain, on absorption of *p*-dialkylamino styryl dyes derived from benzimidazoles.

For preparation of the *p*-dialkylaminostyryl dyes and their diaza analogues, quaternary salts of 2-methyl and 2-methylmercapto benzimidazoles respectively were used. The quaternary salts were prepared by the reaction of the 2-methyl and 2-methylmercapto benzimidazoles with methyl iodide, when the $-\text{NH}-$ group also underwent methylation simultaneously along with quaternary salt formation¹. Hence the quaternisation product was not the simple methiodide but N-methylmethiodide.

The quaternary salts of 2-methyl benzimidazoles were condensed with *p*-dimethyl-amino benzaldehyde in absolute alcohol in presence of piperidine to give rise to *p*-dialkylaminostyryl dyes.

The diaza analogues were prepared from quaternary salts of 2-methylmercapto benzimidazoles by the application of Hunig² reaction. The quaternary salts were converted into hydrazones by reaction with hydrazine hydrate. The hydrazones were then condensed with the following amino aromatic and hydroxy aromatic compounds giving rise to diaza analogues and azo dyes.

- (i) Dimethyl aniline.
- (ii) Diethyl aniline.
- (iii) N, N-Dimethyl- α -naphthylamine.
- (iv) 2-Hydroxy-4-phenyl thiazole.
- (v) 8-Hydroxy quinoline.
- (vi) Sodium salt of 2-naphthol-1-sulphonic acid.

1. J. L. B. Smith, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2288.

2. S. Hunig *et al.*, *Annal. Der Chemie.*, 1959, **628**, 56, 69, 81.

The mechanism for condensation of the hydrazones with *p*-methyl aniline and 2-naphthol-1-sulphonic acid are given below in (a) and (b) respectively.

The absorption data of *p*-dialkylaminostyryl dyes and their corresponding diazo-analogues are given in Table I.

TABLE I

Absorption maxima data of *p*-dialkylamino styryl dyes and their corresponding diazo analogues derived from benzimidazoles.

Sl no	Nature of R	Nature of R'	λ_{\max} in m μ		Shift in λ_{\max} in m μ
			Nature of -X=Y- -CH=CH-	Nature of -N=N-	
1.	Hydrogen	Hydrogen	460	560	100
2.	Methyl	Hydrogen	480	563	83
3.	Methoxy	Hydrogen	485	564	79
4.	Chloro	Hydrogen	470	573	103
5.	Bromo	Hydrogen	460	572	112
6.	Bromo	Bromo	440	556	116
7.	Nitro	Hydrogen	470	620	150

The absorption data have been interpreted in the light of Forster's rule which states that the absorption maximum of a dye will increase with the decreasing tendency of the chain of atoms lying between the auxochromes to take up the characteristic charge.

The examination of the absorption data of these styryl dyes and their diaza analogues shows that bathochromic shift is observed on replacement of $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$ in the chromophoric chain by $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$. This can also be theoretically deduced from Forster's rule. The application of Forster's rule is illustrated by the following:

In the most likely excited structure is $-\overset{\oplus}{\text{C}}\text{H}-$ and not $-\overset{\ominus}{\text{C}}\text{H}-$. When one $-\overset{\oplus}{\text{C}}\text{H}=\text{}$ group is replaced by $=\overset{\oplus}{\text{N}}-$ giving rise to mono aza analogue (II), owing to the greater instability of $-\overset{\oplus}{\text{N}}-$ as compared to $-\overset{\oplus}{\text{C}}\text{H}-$ bathochromic shift is expected according to the requirements of Forster's rule. By extension of the same argument, further bathochromic shift will be expected on replacement of another $=\text{CH}-$ by $-\text{N}=\text{}$ giving rise to diaza analogues.

Table I indicates that the experimental results are consistent with the conclusions derived from Forster's rule.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Table II describes the analytical data of some quaternary methiodides of 2-methyl benzimidazoles, which were prepared from the appropriate *p*-substituted-*o*-phenylene diamines according to the method of Cescon and Day³.

The *o*-phenylene diamines were obtained from corresponding *p*-substituted anilines through the successive steps of acetylation, nitration, hydrolysis and the reduction of the resulting *o*-nitro-*p*-substituted anilines with tin and hydrochloric acid⁴

6-nitro-2-methyl benzimidazole was obtained by the nitration of 2-methyl benzimidazole.⁵

The quaternary salts were obtained by heating the 2-methyl benzimidazoles with methyl iodide in a sealed tube. The analytical data of the quaternary methiodides are given in Table II.

3. Cescon and Day, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, **27**, 581.

4. Jackson and Russe, *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1906, **35**, 150.

5. M. A. Phillips, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 1407.

TABLE II

Analytical data of quaternary methiodides of 2-methyl benzimidazoles

Sl. no.	Nature of R	Nature of R'	M. P. °C	Yield %	%Carbon		%H	
					Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1.	Methyl	Hydrogen	189	60	43.81	43.71	4.78	4.96
2.	Chloro	Hydrogen	232	58	37.65	37.2	3.66	3.72
3.	Bromo	Hydrogen	170	63	33.1	32.7	3.41	3.27
4.	Methoxy	Hydrogen	127	55	41.83	41.52	4.81	4.72
5.	Nitro	Hydrogen	161	48	35.73	36.04	3.65	3.604
6.	Bromo	Bromo	208	50	27.4	26.91	2.53	2.467

p-Dialkylamino styryl dyes were obtained from the corresponding quaternary salts by conventional methods. Their analytical and absorption maxima data are given in Table III.

TABLE III

Analytical and absorption maxima data of *p*-dialkylamino styryl dyes derived from benzimidazoles.

Sl. no.	Nature of R	Nature of R'	M. P. °C	Yield %	λ_{max} m μ	%C		%H	
						Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1.	Hydrogen	Hydrogen	89	45	460	54.24	54.42	5.31	5.25
2.	Methyl	Hydrogen	93	35	480	55.43	55.43	5.46	5.54
3.	Chloro	Hydrogen	78	57	470	50.38	50.27	4.71	4.63
4.	Bromo	Hydrogen	183	50	460	45.59	45.78	4.15	4.22
5.	Methoxy	Hydrogen	69	58	485	52.93	53.46	5.28	5.34
6.	Nitro	Hydrogen	147	55	470	48.57	49.14	4.46	4.52
7.	Bromo	Bromo	113	38	440	39.38	39.51	3.49	3.46

Table IV describes the analytical data of some quaternary methiodides of 2-methyl mercapto benzimidazoles which were obtained by the condensation of appropriate *p*-substituted *o*-phenylene diamines with potassium ethyl xanthate⁶ and subsequent methylation of the resulting 2-mercapto compounds with dimethyl sulphate.

The quaternary methiodides were obtained by heating the 2-methyl mercapto benzimidazoles with methyl iodide in a sealed tube.

TABLE IV

Analytical data of quaternary methiodides of 2-methyl mercapto benzimidazoles.

Sl no.	Nature of R	Nature of R'	M. P. °C	Yield %	% C		% H	
					Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1.	Hydrogen	Hydrogen	131	63	38.32	37.51	4.07	4.06
2.	Methyl	Hydrogen	110	65	39.25	39.53	4.51	4.49
3.	Chloro	Hydrogen	119	65	33.47	33.86	3.42	3.38
4.	Bromo	Hydrogen	135	67	29.92	30.07	3.16	3.00
5.	Methoxy	Hydrogen	108	50	37.64	37.71	4.35	4.28
6.	Nitro	Hydrogen	141	61	33.03	32.88	3.41	3.28
7.	Bromo	Bromo	149	58	25.24	25.11	2.26	2.30

Preparation of N, N-dimethyl benzimidazole hydrazone: Quaternary benzimidazole methiodide (1.6 g.) was heated with 60% aqueous hydrazine hydrate (3.55 g.) at 80° for one hour. The mixture was poured into water when the N, N-dimethyl benzimidazole hydrazone precipitated out. The precipitated solid was collected and dried at 90°. M.P. -115°. Yield—61%. (%C—Found 66.48, reqd. 66.67; % H—Found 7.41, reqd. 7.408).

Other compounds of this series were prepared by the above method. Their analytical data are given in Table V.

TABLE V

Analytical data of N, N-dimethyl benzimidazole hydrazones.

Sl. no.	Nature of R	Nature of R'	M.P. °C	Yield %	%C		%H	
					Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1.	Methyl	Hydrogen	190	63	68.43	68.19	7.87	7.95
2.	Chloro	Hydrogen	182	61	55.23	54.95	5.68	5.6
3.	Bromo	Hydrogen	195	56	45.27	44.81	4.63	4.56
4.	Methoxy	Hydrogen	170	65	62.59	62.50	7.34	7.29
5.	Nitro	Hydrogen	135	45	52.34	52.17	5.39	5.31
6.	Bromo	Bromo	179	62	34.62	33.75	3.20	3.12

Preparation of diaza analogues of styryl dyes with amino aromatic compounds: N,N-dimethyl benzimidazole hydrazone (4.4 g.) and dimethyl aniline (3.025 g.) were dissolved in 80 cc. of 1N hydrochloric acid, and 3.5 mg. ferrous sulphate were then added. Hydrogen peroxide (1.870 g; 30 vols.) was then added at 30° when the dye started forming immediately. Formic acid (20 g.) was then added and the reaction mixture was heated on a water bath at 70—80° for five minutes. The solution was then filtered and to the filtrate 5 g. of sodium iodide dissolved in minimum quantity of water was added. The dye separated out as iodide on cooling. It was filtered and washed with a little cold sodium iodide solution and dried over silica gel.

M.P.—246°. Yield—58% (% C—Found 48.52, Reqd. 48.45; % H. found 4.65, Reqd. 4.75).

The dye showed maximum absorption at 560 m μ in ethanol.

A series of diaza analogues were prepared from the hydrazones by the above method. Their m.p., analytical and absorption data are given in Table VI.

Preparation of Azo dyes with hydroxy aromatic compounds: The hydrazone compounds were condensed with 2-hydroxy-4-phenyl thiazole and 8-hydroxy quinoline in the above manner to give rise to azo dyes. Their m.p., analytical and absorption maxima data are given in Table VI.

TABLE VI

Analytical and absorption maxima data of Azo dyes derived from different benzimidazoles and different amino and hydroxy aromatic compounds.

Sl. no.	Nature of R	Nature of R'	Nature of A	M.P. °C	Yield %	λ_{\max} in m/ μ	%C		%H	
							Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1.	Hydrogen.	Hydrogen	<i>p</i> -Dimethylamino phenyl	246	58	560	48.52	48.45	4.68	4.75
2.	Methyl	„	„	164	55	563	49.53	49.66	4.96	5.06
3.	Chloro	„	„	237	48	573	44.97	44.78	4.16	4.17
4.	Bromo	„	„	221	50	572	40.62	40.80	3.73	3.80
5.	Methoxy	„	„	111	55	564	47.85	47.89	4.80	4.88
6.	Nitro	„	„	178	45	620	43.67	43.77	4.14	4.08
7.	Bromo	Bromo	„	145	54	556	35.47	35.23	3.02	3.11
8.	Hydrogen	Hydrogen	„	190	46	558	50.63	50.78	5.36	5.35
9.	Methyl	„	„	160	55	556	51.27	51.83	5.51	5.62
10.	Chloro	„	„	236	63.5	575	47.11	47.17	4.67	6.76
11.	Bromo	„	„	171	48	574	42.68	43.18	4.28	4.36
12.	Methoxy	„	„	174	53	563	50.57	50.10	5.40	4.43
13.	Nitro	„	„	145	54	556	45.30	46.15	4.71	4.65
14.	Bromo	Bromo	„	139	57	620	37.27	37.56	3.64	3.62

TABLE VI (Contd.)

Sl. no.	Nature of R	Nature of R'	Nature of A	M.P. °C	Yield %	λ_{\max} in m μ	% C Found	% C Req'd.	% H Found	% H Req'd.
15.	Hydrogen	Hydrogen	N,N-dimethyl-amino naphthyl	126	48	600	52.75	52.51	4.58	4.67
16.	Methyl	„	„	163	55	528	54.38	54.44	4.88	4.95
17.	Chloro	„	„	230	50	576	49.13	49.85	4.08	4.15
18.	Bromo	„	„	218	50	553	44.86	45.81	3.90	3.82
19.	Methoxy	„	„	166	58	576	51.63	53.70	4.84	4.79
20.	Nitro	„	„	123	43	600	46.48	48.84	3.93	4.07
21.	Bromo	Bromo	„	145	56	518	39.92	40.05	3.23	3.18
22.	Hydrogen	Hydrogen	5-(8-hydroxy quinoliny)	249	48	558	49.60	48.54	3.62	39.59
23.	Methyl	„	„	166	48	534	49.99	49.67	3.88	3.92
24.	Chloro	„	„	231	51	562	45.30	45.05	3.18	3.13
25.	Bromo	„	„	224	52	560	41.97	41.23	2.84	2.86
26.	Methoxy	„	„	168	49	540	48.24	47.99	3.72	3.70
27.	Bromo	Bromo	„	113	49	530	36.71	35.83	2.38	2.32
28.	Hydrogen	Hydrogen	5-(2-hydroxy 4-phenylthiazolyl)	179	50	520	45.86	45.29	3.42	3.36
29.	Methyl	„	„	173	51	520	47.16	46.43	3.71	3.67
30.	Chloro	„	„	205	47	652	42.12	42.24	2.95	2.98
31.	Bromo	„	„	163	54	520	45.29	44.96	3.61	3.55
32.	Methoxy	„	„	160	53	560	41.75	41.38	2.90	2.87
33.	Bromo	Bromo	„	142	53	520	34.13	34.02	2.24	2.21
34.	Hydrogen	Hydrogen	1-(2-hydroxy naphthyl)	233	48	490	52.15	51.35	3.76	3.83
35.	Methyl	„	„	251	45	490	52.85	52.40	4.12	4.15
36.	Chloro	„	„	253	53	460	48.30	47.64	3.40	3.34
37.	Bromo	„	„	259	46	489	51.24	50.63	3.97	4.01
38.	Methoxy	„	„	245	53	480	46.85	46.62	3.32	3.27
39.	Bromo	Bromo	„	216	45	470	58.15	57.87	2.51	2.49

Preparation of 'Red dye' with 2-naphthol-1-sulphonic acid: N, N-dimethyl benzimidazole hydrazone (4.4 g.) and sodium salt of 2-naphthol-1-sulphonic acid (7.38 g.) were dissolved in 50 cc. of methanol, 25 cc. of water added and the mixture was stirred. The temperature was kept at 8-10°. Potassium ferricyanide (3.617 g.) and sodium carbonate (2.65 g.) dissolved in minimum quantity of water were then added, when the dye formed immediately. After 15 minutes the mixture was diluted with 25 cc. of water and the dye was filtered off. The dye was washed with water and dried over silica gel in vacuum. It was crystallised from chlorobenzene, M.P.—233°. Yield—48%. (%C.—Found 52.1, Req'd. 51.35; %H. Found 3.76, Req'd. 3.828).

The analytical and absorption maxima data of the azo dyes prepared by the above method are given in Table VI.

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